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BIOAVAILABILITY OF BIOACTIVE FOOD INGREDIENTS—BIBLIOMETRIC INSIGHTS ON CURRENT RESEARCH FOCUSED ON THE ROLE AND APPLICATION OF BILE ACIDS

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Bile acids participate in the complex mechanism of solubilization and absorption of lipid molecules in the intestines. Although they are approved for supplementation in several diseases and often investigated as drug carriers, their use as additives to improve the bioavailability of compounds in food is not common. This bibliometric study aimed to examine the publication records of research on improved bioavailability of food compounds, and to search for the applications of the bile acids and their derivatives in the field of food science technology. A literature search was done in August 2021 using the Web of Science (WOS) online database (Clarivate Analytics, Philadelphia, PA, USA), choosing the following set of keywords: Topic = (food OR nutrient* OR dietary OR nutraceutical*) AND (bioavailability OR bioaccessibility OR liberation OR absorption). Only research articles assigned to the WOS category Food Science Technology were taken into consideration. A total of 10,098 publications were obtained, published in the period from 1994 to 2021. An increasing trend in the annual number of publications was observed, which reached its maximum in 2020 with 1171 publications. Most of publications came from China and the USA, followed by Spain, India and Brazil. The publications were supported by various funding agencies such as the National Natural Foundation of China (8%), European Commission (4%) and National Council for Scientific and Technological Development, Brazil (3%). Further limitation of the WOS search by Title= *cholic OR bile acid, gave 19 results, ranging from 2004 to 2021, with most publications (4) published in 2020. Seven publications examined the role of fiber-enriched foods in bile acid binding, while others evaluated the effects of food ingredients on bile acid transporters, synthesis, gene expression, or effects on intestinal microbiota. Only one study suggested improvement of polyphenols bioavailability due to bile acids binding. This study showed that the research on food compound bioavailability is current, while the application of the bile acid micellar systems as food additives is not widely recognized and gives space for development by implementing the knowledge gained in field of drug delivery.

Keywords: bile acids; bioavailability; foodcompounds; additives; bibliometric analysis